

Progress of rice blast in Kihogo Red and Faya Theresa with and without fungicide spray in Tanzania.

variety interaction was also highly significant for yield, but not for 1,000-grain weight.

The weather during the experiment was drier than usual. Moreover, much of Tanzania's rice is dryland on which blast is severe. □

Effect of blast on rice yields in Tanzania.

Cultivar	Paddy yield			1,000-paddy grain wt		
	Sprayed (t/ha)	Unsprayed (t/ha)	Reduction (%)	Sprayed (g)	Unsprayed (g)	Reduction (%)
Kihogo Red	2.70	2.59	4.1	31.41	30.29	1.1
Faya Theresa	3.04	2.49	18.1**	27.37	24.28	11.3**

** = highly significant difference ($P = 0.01$).

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Varietal resistance to white leafhopper

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White leafhopper (WLH) *Cofana spectra* (Distant) is a major rice pest in India. Nymphs and adults suck plant sap and cause stunting followed by drying.

Glasshouse-cultured insects were used to study varietal resistance to WLH. Cages 45 × 45 × 60 cm, with wooden frames, glass tops and doors, and wire mesh side walls were used. From 50 to 70 field-collected WLH adults of both sexes were released in each cage and confined for 2 to 3 days for oviposition on 45- to 50-day-old potted TN1 rice plants. Plants with eggs were then moved to separate cages. Nymphs were transferred to fresh TN1 plants when necessary. A continuous adult population was maintained.

Seeds of test accessions were soaked in water for 24 h. Seeds sprouted in darkness. Three days after soaking sprouted seed were sown in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden flats filled with 5-7 cm of soil. Each flat held nine test accessions and the susceptible check TN1. One week after

sowing seedlings were thinned to 20/row and wooden flats were placed in galvanized 62- × 47- × 1.5-cm iron trays filled with 10 cm water. Fifteen days after sowing, 3 WLH adults/seedling were released on the flat and covered with a 55- × 45- × 50-cm nylon mesh cage. Dead insects were replaced with live ones.

Damage was rated by row when 90% of the TN1 plants were killed. The following rating scale was developed.

Resistance rating of rice accessions to *C. spectra*, Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Damage rating
CO 2	2.35
CO 29	2.40
ASD5	2.90
CH2	3.00
ASD13	3.00
ASD12	3.20
ASD3	3.30
ADT14	3.40
IET5741	3.40
ASD10	3.47
ASD2	3.50
ASD14	3.50
CO 25	3.66
Vazhaipoo Samba	3.66
IET6315	3.80
CO 22	3.85

Grade	Criterion	Rating
0	No visible damage	Immune/tolerant
1	First leaf tip yellowing	Highly resistant
3	First leaf drying and second leaf tip yellowing, followed by drying	Resistant
5	Yellowing of all leaves or pronounced stunting or both	Moderately resistant
7	Wilting, followed by drying of more than 50% of the plants	Susceptible
9	All plants dead	Highly susceptible

With this scale, 16 of 39 rice accessions screened were resistant to moderately resistant (see table).

Detailed studies of the resistant acces-

sions CO 2, CO 29, and ASD5 have shown that nonpreference for orientation and oviposition, and antibiosis are principal resistance components. □